

Review Biochemical Changes in Different Tissues of Freshwater Fish, *Channa orientalis* After Toxic Exposure

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Abstract

Alteration in physiological functions and of body structures are the most important detectable parameters of pollution effects at individual as well as population level. The LC₅₀ value of Confidor and Bavistin freshwater fish, *Channa orientalis* (Schneider) exposed to concentration of imidacloprid Confidor and Carbendazim Bavistin (0.9ppm and 0.10 ppm for 96 hrs.) along with control animals were studied for acute exposure 24, 48, 72, 96 hrs. Behavioral changes like, rapid opercular movement, large mucous covering over body, erratic swimming and jerky movements were observed in the experimental fishes. For biochemical analysis, fishes were exposed to lethal concentration of Confidor and Bavistin. After this, tissues like liver and gonad were taken from the control and experimental groups and estimation of cholesterol was done by Knobil method. It has been observed that, cholesterol concentrations were decreased in experimental liver and gonad as compare to control.

Keywords: Biochemical Profile, Liver, Gonad, Confidor, Bavistin.

1. Introduction:

Exposure to pesticide residues has been associated with elevated levels of ammonium, nitrite, nitrate, and sulfate in aquatic systems, posing significant risks to both ecological integrity and human health (Abu Qamar *et al.*, 2024; Kumar *et al.*, 2023). Air breathing fishes have a unique position in fishing industry due to their hardy nature and easy maintenance. In addition to the aquatic oxygen they are privilege to respire atmospheric oxygen as a result of which they can be easily handled and kept in living condition for longer duration without much precaution. Water pollution has become a serious problem throughout the world, it is unfortunate that the rivers are being increasingly used as natural dustbin for discharge of all sort of community and industrial wastes, Binukumari *et al.*, 2015. Various types of pesticides

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including insecticides, herbicides, fungicides etc are used for agricultural production, but these agricultural runoffs finally reached in the water bodies and pollute the non-target aquatic biota, Gijare and Tantarale, 2014, Khan and Francis, 2005. Bioaccumulation of these pesticides threatens the long term survival of fishes by disrupting the ecological relationship between organisms and loss of biodiversity (Abedi *et al.*, 2013).

The continues overuse of the pesticide and indiscriminate dumping of untreated wastes into aquatic environments brings about physical, chemical and biological deterioration of water bodies (Benjamin and Thatheyus, 2012). *Channa orientalis* is a popular food fish in all over the India including Khandesh region. Economically this fish has high nutritive value. Confidor acts as systemic insecticide a powerful neonicotinoid that controls sucking pests containing Imidaclopride 17.80% SL. It is highly toxic to an acute basis to aquatic animals and Bavistin acts as broad spectrum systemic fungicide containing Carbendazim 50% hence widely used to control fungal diseases in crops. In the present work freshwater fish, *C. orientalis* was selected to study the toxic effects of Confidor and Bavistin on behavior and tissues like liver and gonad. The runoff from treated areas enters the river and aquaculture ponds that are supplied by rivers and adversely affect the quality of water surfaces and creates hazards for aquatic life resulting in serious damage to non-target species, including fishes, Sasaki, *et al.*, 1997. Fishes are rich in high quality, balanced and easily digestible protein, vitamins and polyunsaturated fatty acids. Ravichandran *et al.*, 2011 fishes as good source of immense antimicrobial peptide that defends against dreadful human pathogens. Biochemical studies helps to find out the effects of pollutants on different metabolism of fish, Kajare *et.al.* 2000.

The fish species selected for present study is of economic value and readily available throughout the year and it stands captivity well. Fishes are the bioindicator species of the aquatic environment, because they are sensitive to any change in the water quality. It represents the natural population in the river and water bodies. The present study was undertaken to analyze the impact of acute concentration of Confidor and Bavistin in liver, gonad, of fish, *Channa orientalis*.

2. Materials and Methods:

Medium sized fresh water Healthy fishes weighing between 20-30 gms and size 5-7 cm. *Channa orientalis* were collected from Shiven River area Nandurbar Dist. Nandurbar. They were transferred to **Conference Special Issue on "Current Advancements in Biodiversity of Flora and Fauna (CABFF-2026)"**
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the glass aquarium and acclimatized to the laboratory conditions in the department of Zoology for two weeks and inspected for any possible injury or infection. Injured fishes were avoided. Only healthy fishes of different weight with length group of 10 mm range were selected. The physico-chemical parameters of the water used by the methods APHA and AWWA, 2005. Fishes were washed with 0.1% of potassium permanganate (KMnO₄) solution to avoid dermal infection. They were then rinsed in water. Dead fish were removed immediately that such mortality may deplete dissolved oxygen with resultant effect on other fishes. During acclimatization fishes were fed with pieces of live earthworm on alternate days. Water also changed once in every day. The experiment was conducted natural and photoperiod of temperature $27.1 \pm 3.20^{\circ}\text{C}$, Conductivity- 0.65 ± 0.3 , Dissolved O₂- 6.4 ± 1.1 (ml/L), pH- 8.65 ± 0.3 , Acidity- 2.7 ± 0.1 , Alkalinity- 45.1 ± 0.5 , Total hardness- 67.6 ± 0.3 . The Lc₅₀ value of Confidor and Bavistin (0.9ppm and 0.10 ppm for 96 hrs.) was determined.

The stock solution of Confidor was prepared. From stock solutions of Confidor and Bavistin different concentrations were prepared. In toxicity bioassay test, fishes were divided into several groups, each group comprising of 10 fishes. One group was considered as experimental group exposed to reagent grade of Confidor and Bavistin for 24, 48, 72, and 96 hrs for acute exposure. Fishes were fed regularly with fish food and water was changed every day in the control as well as treated group. Mortality was recorded during 96 hrs. The data collected was then analyzed statistically by means of Probit analysis method on transforming toxicity curve (%mortality versus concentration) into regression line. Mortality in probit /log of concentration by Finney, (1971) method simplified by Busvine, (1971) which allows the average medium lethal concentration, LC₅₀ was calculated for 96 hrs. The cholesterol was estimated by using Knobil method (Knobil *et.al.*, 1954) from the tissue in control and experimental fishes. Pure dry ash free cholesterol was used as a standard.

During the experiment the behavioral changes were observed. To count the mortality, the fishes were examined individually and those, which have lost the ability of opercular movement and did not respond to the tactile stimulus, were considered as dead. Each biochemical parameter was assessed in five individual animals. The fishes were starved for one day prior to experimentation in order to avoid the metabolic differences, if any due to differential feeding and food reserves. Then the fishes

were cut open to ascertain the sex. The liver and gonads were pooled up from the fishes. After noting down the sex and weight of the fishes, the tissues were quickly weighed.

3. Results and Discussion:

The acute toxicity of Confidor and Bavistin as percent mortality in different concentrations are shown in Table 1. The changes in biochemical composition of liver and gonad of freshwater fish *Channa orientalis*, exposed to acute treatment of Confidor and Bavistin were studied along with experimental animals with respect to the percentage of cholesterol in wet tissue. The cholesterol content of the liver and gonad was found to be decreased after acute treatment by Confidor and Bavistin. The percent decrease of cholesterol in liver, after 96hrs treatment with Confidor and Bavistin was 4.834 to 1.441 % and 4.986 to 3.2499 % respectively. The average cholesterol content of gonad was decreased from 5.087 to 2.7860% and 5.985 to 4.0398 % respectively. The percent depletion in cholesterol content was found in the liver and gonad after pesticidal stress as a period of exposure increased. The animals treated with Confidor are more pronounced as compared to the Bavistin. Results of cholesterol alteration are summarized in Table 2 & fig. 1 & 2.

Table 1: The acute toxicity of Confidor and Bavistin as % mortality in different concs.

Toxicant	Conc. in ppm	No. of fish alive out of ten	Mortality (%)	Probit Kill	Lc50 value in ppm
Confidor	5	08	20	4.15	0.9
	6	07	30	4.47	
	7	05	50	5.10	
	8	03	70	5.52	
	10	00	100	8.09	
Bavisti	5	09	10	3.71	0.10
	6	08	20	4.40	
	7	06	40	4.74	
	8	05	50	5	
	10	03	70	5.52	

The mortality of the experimental fish is depending on dose. Behavioral changes are seen during stress in the experimental organism as compared to the control. Experimental fish's shows hyper excitation, restlessness, swimming with jerky and irregular movements and tried to come out of aquarium. Behavioral pattern of aquatic organism that have been tested or investigated during the last

hundred years of aquatic toxicity testing deals with the avoidance of reaction, swimming with jerky and irregular movements and schooling behavior, level of swimming, and respiratory behavior like rate of operculum movement to extract more oxygen to meet the increased energy demand to withstand the toxicity etc. by Veeraiah and Durga Prasad,(2001). Behavior of the animal can serve as the link between physiological and ecological processes reported by Graham and Sloman, (2004). Increase in the frequency of surfacing phenomenon due to hypoxia condition difficulty to respire in the media.

Table 2. Effects of Confidor & Bavistin on Cholestrol content in liver of *Channa orintalis* during period of acute exposure

Tissue	Treatment	Acute Exposure			
		24h	48 h	72 h	96 h
Liver	Control	5.980	5.964	5.840	5.762
		1.84380	1.69701	1.26600	1.47940
Liver	Confidor	4.834	3.715	2.571	1.441
		1.71352	1.38700	1.3756	1.1857
Liver	Bavistin	4.986	4.0008	3.890	3.2499
		1.76244	2.3772	2.1437	1.945

Values expressed as % of wet wt. of tissue; wet weight (mean \pm SD)[#]

= P<0.05, ## = P<0.01, ### = P < 0.001

Table 3. Effects of Confidor & Bavistin on Cholesterol content in gonad of *Channa orintalis* during period of acute exposure

Tissue	Treatment	Acute Exposure			
		24h	48 h	72 h	96 h
Gonad	Control	5.287	5.2069	5.1043	2.7882
		1.79904	1.76167	1.55228	1.63875
Gonad	Confidor	5.087	4.2541	3.1142	2.7860
		1.27527	1.42003	1.36395	1.63875
Gonad	Bavistin	5.985	5.164	4.1023	4.0398
		1.934846	2.25618	1.71818	1.94056

Values expressed as % of wet wt. of tissue; wet weight (mean \pm SD)[#]

= P<0.05, ## = P<0.01, ### = P < 0.001

Activities were reduced, the fish settled to the bottom, increased mucous secretion with slimy white layer, increased and decreased opercular movements were seen. Fishes showed rapid zigzag movement with sudden jerks and avoidance of response. It seems that fish loses balance, as a result

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of influence of toxicant. Before death, the body color of the fish turned faint due to loss of skin pigmentation, and fish died with open mouth. Fishes exposed to Bavistin shows dark coloration; less excitations, aerial excursion also few, opercula movements were increased, mucous secretion was copious. The examination of dead fish exhibited open opercula, bent body, which gill and copious mucous with signs of bleeding.

Fig-1: Effects of Confidor & Bavistin on Cholestrol content in liver of *Channa orientalis* during period of acute exposure

Acute toxicity tests are useful in providing rapid estimates of the concentrations of toxicants that cause direct irreversible harm to the organism (Parrish, 1985). Behavioral characteristics are obviously sensitive indicators of toxicants effect. It is necessary, however, to select behavioral indices of monitoring that relate to the organisms behavior in the field in order to derive a more accurate assessment of the hazards that a contaminant may pose in natural system (Marigoudar *et al.*, 2009). Jerky movements of fish were due to the nervous imbalance whereas increased opercular movements were done for respiration. Arillo and Melodia (1990), the mucous secretion all over the body on exposure to pollutants has an ameliorative effect against the toxicants. A profuse mucous secretion could cause a hardship for aerial breathing in the medium because the lamellar fusion will reduce the surface area for gaseous exchange (Parithabhanu, 2013).

Pesticidal toxication produce biochemical changes in organs of fish and for curing the stress an organism need sufficient energy which is obtained from reserve materials like glycogen, protein and lipid. When the stress is mild then only stored glycogen is used as source of energy, but when the stress is strong at that time the stored energy in protein and lipid may be used. Hence, lipid is an important constituent of animal play an active role in energy metabolism.

Fig-2: Effects of Confidor & Bavistin on Cholesterol content in gonad of *Channa orientalis* during period of acute exposure

Lipids are important dietary constituents and it serves as condensed reserve of energy. Depletion in cholesterol content suggests that organic reserves seem to have utilized at longer exposure because the animals have no longer adopt to pesticidal stress conditions. Lipid content of fish reduces with increasing concentration of pollutants and this reduction may have been due to the utilization of lipid energy demand under stress condition. Gijare and Tantarपाले, (2014), found declined trend of cholesterol in the liver and muscle of freshwater fish, *Ophiocephalus punctatus* after exposure of the sublethal concentration of cypermethrin. They state that, the reduced cholesterol level is due to the inhibition of cholesterol biosynthesis in the liver and reduced absorption of dietary cholesterol. Binukumari *et al.*, (2015), studied the effects of Ekalux on the biochemical parameters of the fish, *L. rohita* and they recorded low level of total cholesterol in tissues like liver, kidney, gill, muscles. They suggested that lipid might have been channeled for energy production for other metabolic functions in which these products play a role during stress.

Similar results were also recorded earlier by various scientists. Govindan *et al.*, (1994), reported decrease in lipid content in liver, muscle and brain of *Gambusia affinis* exposed to a pesticide phosphamidon. Abiram *et al.*, (2012), recorded decline in the level of lipid in *Terapon jarbua* after toxicity of endosulfan. Waghmare and Wani, (2014), recorded cholesterol depletion in liver and gonads of freshwater fish, *L. rohita* after exposure to insecticide polo. Sivandan and Binukumari, (2021), recorded lipid depletion in *L. rohita* after malathion intoxication. The present investigation reveals that insecticide Confidor and Bavistin induce the number of abnormal behavior and alteration in cholesterol content in liver and gonad of fish, *Channa orientalis*.

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